

Three questions to Unitelma Sapienza

Interview with Annarita Colasante, responsible for the socio-economic analysis in BioReCer

Why are consumers reluctant to use bio-based products (BBP) and especially products made of biological waste?

Based on the literature about consumers' preferences for upcycled products (especially food) and based on the main feedback we got from stakeholders' focus groups we may conclude that consumers consider bio-based products made of biological waste as inferior goods and, furthermore, they are also worried about the potential risk for their health.

How can consumers be convinced to use BBPs and which role do certificates/labels play?

The role of certifications and labels in the literature is well known since they increase consumers' trust toward biological and organic products even though there is a not negligible problem of greenwashing. I believe that reliable certifications (i.e., from national or international third-party bodies) could also improve consumers' acceptance of bio-based products made of biological waste.

Why is the valorisation and use of organic waste beneficial for the EU bioeconomy and how will EU citizens and the environment benefit?

In my opinion, and based on the opinions of some representatives of both bio-industries and biomass producers, organic waste represents a valuable resource for the EU bioeconomy and it should be better exploited. The main barrier we are aware of is legislation that is country-specific and makes it hard to introduce this resource in the circular production process. Since many organic resources could be converted into raw materials, the positive environmental impact would be notable and it will obviously generate a domino effect on citizens well-being.